

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE CREATIVE MATHEMATICAL PROBLEM-SOLVING PRACTICES IN IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE IN GENERAL MATHEMATICS OF THE GRADE 11 LEARNERS IN CALAUAG WEST DISTRICT, DIVISION OF QUEZON

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The Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance in General Mathematics of the Grade 11 Learners in Calauag West District, Division of Quezon

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Abstract

This study assessed the effectiveness of creative mathematical problem-solving practices in enhancing the performance of Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics in the Calauag West District, Division of Quezon, for the School Year 2023–2024. It examined the level of creative problem-solving practices in terms of flexibility, fluency, originality, and elaboration, and evaluated their impact on performance in topics such as logarithmic functions, simple and compound interest, functions and their graphs, and basic business mathematics. The study also explored significant agreements in the evaluation of these practices among different groups of respondents and formulated policy recommendations based on the findings. Using a descriptive-evaluative-correlational research method and total enumeration sampling, the study analyzed data with tools such as weighted mean, rank order, and Kendall Coefficient of Concordance W. Results showed that creative mathematical problem-solving practices were rated "Much Evident," with elaboration receiving the highest mean score and fluency the lowest. Originality exhibited a significant agreement in rank order among aspects evaluated. The practices were also deemed "Much Effective" in improving performance, with basic business mathematics ranking highest, followed closely by other topics. However, no significant agreement was observed in rank order of effectiveness across respondent groups, except for logarithmic functions. Key policy recommendations include providing learners with access to interactive tools, professional development for teachers, and promoting creative and critical thinking in educational policies. Schools and the Department of Education are encouraged to allocate resources for initiatives fostering problem-solving skills. The study concluded that creative problem-solving practices significantly enhance learner performance and recommends their continued use and enhancement. Future research should examine their long-term impact, teacher training effectiveness, and applicability to other subjects.

Keywords: *creative mathematical problem-solving practices, performance*

Introduction

Mathematics is a pattern of thinking and organizing as well as logical proof about shape, structure, number, and concept related to everyday life. In accordance with one educational goal to actualize the individual ability, then one of the existing abilities in mathematics education is a mathematical problem-solving practice. Mathematics education should focus on the development of creative thinking and problem-solving skills where the students are free to express and think about their own original possible solutions. Creative problem-solving ability is the high-dimensional human ability or skills to think up something new and draw much attention in every field of education.

Mathematical creative problem-solving practices are one of the practices needed by the students, to formulate and solve problems according to the appropriateness and evolved concepts of mathematical problems in more flexible, fluent and original creative responses to see the relevance of math with other subjects as well as in real life. Students are said to be able to solve mathematical problems if they can understand, choose the right strategy, and then implement them in problem solving.

Teachers become the focus, because they directly affect, assess and develop student ability to be a smart, skillful and moral human. Therefore, the efforts to improve student learning outcome cannot be separated from the efforts of teacher ability to teach and use the models in mathematics learning. Various learning models have been applied by the math teachers in schools for communicating the concept of the subject material, but the use of learning models is not necessarily creating a good learning outcome. Measuring the mathematics performance of students is challenging since students' performance is a product of socio-economic and environmental factors.

Performance in mathematics involves a complex interaction of factors on school outcome. Studies on mathematical performance have been found to improve the levels of mathematics achievement and deliver high quality education in school organization. It cannot be denied that students' performance in mathematics is greatly influenced not only by student and teacher but also the mathematical creative problem-solving practices towards mathematics. That's why the researcher desires to find out the level of mathematical creative problem-solving practices and students' perception towards mathematics.

This study was anchored on the following legal basis, Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution, Section 1 states that:

The state shall promote and protect the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all.

Republic Act 10533 or also known as the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013" mandating all teachers to maximize learning on literacy and numeracy among learners with relevant teaching strategies that ensure high learning outcomes that could be the performance tasks or written outputs on the part of the student learners; Republic Act 9155, otherwise known as the "Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001" declares the policy of the state to protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality basic education and to make such education accessible to all by providing all Filipino children a free and compulsory education in the elementary level and free education in the high school level. Such an education should also include an alternative learning system for out-of-school youth and adult learners. It shall be the goal of basic education to provide them with the skills, knowledge and values they need to become caring, self-reliant, productive and patriotic citizens. This was the basis for the implementation of Education for All program of the Department of Education known as the EFA goals which were meant to eradicate literacy in the country but failed to do so; the Education for All (EFA) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that offers a long term vision for better health and education, sustainable lifestyles, strong partnerships, and shared commitments; Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA) that aims to improve the quality of education in the Philippines and attain the two most important frameworks in the field of education.

With this, the actions must start in the classroom or the learning environment where not only are there few, but all the students must be motivated to learn. Thus, the use of active learning may appear to be very useful in multi-modality of implementing mathematics curriculum. From the student-centered view, all things must be done in the classroom to facilitate the active processing of the curriculum contents. It does not matter what the teacher does, but it matters what the learners are doing that leads to learning the desired learning goals for the day.

Moreover, Republic Act No. 10612, which focuses mainly on providing the state with quality education through the science and mathematics teachers at the secondary level, would encourage more learners to pursue careers in science and technology. Also, this act implies strengthening mathematics teaching among secondary school teachers. From that article, providing new and highly promising teaching strategy must be given priority for the development of research. The significant findings served as the steppingstone for enhancing the learning process in Mathematics particularly the Grade 8 Learners handled by the researcher herself. As every school wants to improve the quality of graduates, teaching the Learners the different Mathematical concepts in times of distance learning modality using Podcast can improve their academic performance and digital presentations of materials. In doing so, teaching the learners not just in memorizing and recalling mathematical concepts but helping them acquire more knowledge and skills in solving problems, adaptation, critical thinking and digital activities is imperative. (Nepomuceno 2018 as cited from the study of Lieberman & Pointer Mace).

Moreover, the Department of Education demands the entire teaching process to be flexible, ensuring the mastery of knowledge and skills, every Grade Level based on spirally progressive approach, the Republic Act 10533, Article 7 (Teacher Education and trainings), which aimed to ensure that the enhanced basic education program meets the demand for quality teachers and school leaders. Therefore, the Department of Education and the Commission on Higher Education, in collaboration with relevant partners in government, academe, industry, and non-governmental organizations, shall conduct teacher education and training programs.

To propel further its new direction to resolve basic education challenges, the Department of Education (DepEd) on Thursday, May 25, unveiled the seven priority points for the intervention in support of its "MATATAG" Agenda.

Vice President and Secretary Sara Duterte stated that:

As we work towards the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals in basic education, we must acknowledge that no organization or government can achieve them alone

"We need strong partnerships that involve all actors, including the private sector, civil society, and local communities," she added.

Duterte noted that DepEd's Finance strand plans to capacitate employees on loan management systems and host financial literacy programs for DepEd personnel and learners. The School Infrastructure and Facilities strand, on the other hand, will prioritize interventions enabling DepEd to construct and rehabilitate classrooms, build disaster-resilient schools, retrofit classrooms, and provide electrification and connectivity programs.

While the Administration strand plans to digitize forms, enhance existing systems, and provide assistance in its parametric and indemnity insurance for public schools, the Curriculum and Teaching will focus on strengthening the Literacy and Numeracy Programs, reviewing Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education, digitizing national assessments, and strengthening inclusive education programs and teaching approaches.

Duterte also bared the plans of the Human Resources and Organizational Development strand for the development of quality assurance effectiveness, upscaling of the National Educators' Academy of the Philippines, and knowledge sharing from the partners in their expertise as their priority intervention programs.

DepEd's Operations strand, Duterte said, also plans to provide mobile medical and dental clinics, enhanced school-based feeding programs, learner rights and protection mechanisms, mental health programs, learner and youth program development, and the farm-to-table nutrition project of DepEd.

Moreover, the Procurement strand seeks to improve DepEd's procurement processes through continuous capacity building for its personnel and processes digitalization.

Duterte also thanked and recognized the "unwavering commitment" of local government units and its local and Official Development Assistance (ODA) partners who reaffirmed their commitment by signing the "MATATAG Partner Ako" commitment wall.

DepEd Policy Statement is commitment of the Department of Education to provide learners with quality basic education that is accessible, inclusive, and liberating through: Proactive leadership, Shared governance, Evidence-based policies, standards and programs, Responsive and relevant curricula, highly competent and committed officials, teaching and non-teaching personnel, an enabling environment.

As our country embraced K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum, higher demands for better learning, better instruction and better academic performance of learners arise. Although learners are well trained in the curriculum competencies, most of them our learners failed to develop abstraction of information and cannot consolidate and transfer previously taught information to the present lesson. Thus, podcasting holds great potential both as a teaching and learning tool. As a result, the podcasting phenomenon has attracted the attention of educators at all levels. This will help learners become better learners, especially after they are exposed to technology-aided instruction.

In general, this research conforms to Objective IV, Section 1, Article 3 of RA 9155 known as Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 which aimed to ensure all Learning Centers should receive the kind of focused attention they deserve and the kind of educational programs, projects and services they need into taking account the interest of all the members of the community. And to "encourage local initiatives for the improvement of schools and learning centers and to provide the means by which these standards have achieved and sustained.

Furthermore, the mathematics subject aims to teach the most important life skills that the school teaches. No child should leave school without mastering the skills to their full potential. Scientific abilities are essential for a person's ability to grow as an individual, live a fulfilling and happy life, and actively engage in society.

In accordance with this, the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) on which the Philippines ranked 43rd out of 45 participating countries in year 2003. And by this year, 2020 of December, The Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study 2019 (TIMSS) revealed that the Filipino learners lagged behind other countries in the international assessment for mathematics and science for grade 4. The Philippines only scored 297 in mathematics which is significantly lower than any other participating country. Hence, low performance in Mathematics in that competition should be reflected, hence mathematics teachers should use newer and more innovation in teaching the subject to improve our country's standing to the TIMMs especially this time of pandemic.

To work in accordance with the Philippine Education for All (EFA) 2015, a goal and a holistic program of reforms aiming at enhancing the quality of basic education for every Filipino by 2015, it is critical to employ applicable teaching methodologies. Improving learner achievement is very important to generate positive outcomes, especially to work with the provisions of the Schools First Initiative (SFI) of 2004 which is aimed to improve basic education outcomes through a broadly participated, popular movement featuring a wide variety of initiatives. This research study is in consonance with the Basic Education Sector Reform Agenda (BESRA), the policy reforms program that issued the National Competency- Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS).

The usage of podcasts in the classroom has resulted in positive outcomes on the Teacher Strengths and Needs Assessment (TSNA), a teacher evaluation tool based on the overarching notion of teacher professional development. It is a learning tool that encourages instructors to take personal responsibility for their own professional development and improvement.

With the focus of this study, it will help the Department of Education in working with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the country's global target for the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Quality Education. Under goal number 4, which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. It aims to ensure that by 2030 all girls and boys can access equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes.

Hence, this study will help the Department of Education in attaining the Results Based Performance Management System (RPMS) which is a systematic approach for consistent and continuous work improvement. The RPMS allows all employees to assess their performance and seek improvement in the same way that teachers evaluate pupils and provide comments to help them improve.

The Department's training actions were guided by the RPMS results to ensure continual progress. This is part of the Department of Education's commitment to provide high-quality education to our learners.

The district has various accomplishments in the Division of Quezon. Journalism has gone so far on its performance. The teachers in the district participated in division and regional activities as speakers, organizers, demonstrator teachers, and curriculum writers. School heads of Calauag heads attended a series of training and workshops for school. These are just the various achievements of the district. Notable accomplishments also written in research. The researcher also became one of the speakers and facilitators of the said training.

Bradshaw (2017) Developing problem-solving skills in mathematics: a lesson study; Kumar(2018) on Enhancing Students' Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills through Bar Model Visualization Technique; Gürefe, (2018) explored on Mathematical

Language Skills of Mathematics Prospective Teachers; Raisen, (2020) dealt on Mathematical Creativity: A Combination of Domain-general Creative and Domain-specific Mathematical Skills; Mahani, (2019) explored on The Effect of Self-Esteem on Students' Mathematical Communication Skills.

Studying the effectiveness of creative mathematical problem-solving practices in enhance critical thinking and deepen understanding of mathematical concepts, making learning more engaging and enjoyable. They also prepare students for higher education and careers by fostering essential problem-solving and analytical skills.

Moreover, promoting creativity and innovation in problem-solving can lead to improved academic performance in General Mathematics, equipping students with the tools needed for success in both their academic and future professional endeavors.

Research Questions

This study determined the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance in General Mathematics of the Grade 11 learners in Calauag West District, Division of Quezon for School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, this research sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent is the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of:
 - 1.1. flexibility;
 - 1.2. fluency;
 - 1.3. originality; and
 - 1.4. elaboration?
2. How significant is the agreement on the rank orders of the extent level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices of the learners in General Mathematics along the aforementioned aspects?
3. To what extent is the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along:
 - 3.1. logarithmic functions;
 - 3.2. simple interest; and
 - 3.3. compound interest;
 - 3.4. functions and their graphs; and
 - 3.5. basic business mathematics?
4. How significant is the agreement on the rank orders of the extent effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along the different groups of respondents?
5. What policy recommendations can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized the descriptive- evaluative- correlational method in determining the data needed under the present investigation. The descriptive method was designed to gather information about the present existing conditions. The principal aims were to describe the nature of a situation, as it exists at the time of study, and to explore cases of phenomena.

The use of descriptive survey helps obtain the descriptive information that answers the queries set in the problem being posed. The descriptive survey method proceeds to describe certain phenomena. For this reason, this method is described to be "fact finding" or "information gathering" with analytical interpretations.

According to Polit and Hungler, (2011), this method aims to understand the subject, accurately describe its characteristics, and provide a foundation for formulating precise problems and hypotheses for further study.

In similar view, Ariola, (2012) descriptive research involves gathering information about current conditions for description and interpretation, including analysis, comparisons, and identifying trends and relationships.

In this study, the descriptive-evaluative method was used in determining the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance in general mathematics of the Grade 11 learners in Calauag West District.

The correlational method was also used to test significant agreement. Appropriate statistical tools were used to accept or reject the hypothesis of the study.

Respondents

The purposive sampling was used in the choice of its locale of the study, which is the Calauag West District, Division of Quezon. However, total enumeration sampling technique was used in the choice of the of the respondents of the study.

There are ten (10) secondary schools in Calauag West District, and they are divided into three types of schools.

Table 1. *The Respondents of the Study*

<i>Schools</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Big Schools		
1. Calauag National HS	64	39
2. Sto. Domingo National HS	40	25
Sub-Total	104	64
Medium Schools		
1. Bantuliniao Integrated HS	24	15
2. Dr. Arsenio Nicolas NHS	10	6
Sub-Total	34	21
Small Schools		
1. Ananias A. Diamante Integrated National HS	4	2
3. Villa San Isidro NHS	4	2
4. Apad NHS	4	2
5. Lagay NHS	6	4
6. Sto. Angel NHS	7	5
Sub-Total	25	15
Grand Total	163	100

Instrument

Preparation of Questionnaire. The questionnaire was used as the main instrument for gathering the needed data for the investigation.

The formulation and validation of the instrument undergoes the following stages – planning, unity of items, submission to a set of jurors, revision, modification, final printing, and administration of questionnaire for a dry run.

In the planning stage, the researcher determined the components of the instrument.

The questionnaire consists of two parts:

Part I consisted of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of: Flexibility, Fluency, Originality and Elaboration.

Part II consisted of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along: Logarithmic Functions, Simple Interest, Compound Interest, Functions and their Graphs, and Basic Business Mathematics.

Table 2 indicates the Table of Specification of the instrument used in the study.

Table 2. *Table of Specifications*

<i>Contents</i>	<i>No. of Items</i>	<i>Item Placement</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Part I- The level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics			
1. Flexibility	11	1-11	11
2. Fluency	11	12-22	11
3. Originality	11	23-33	11
4. Elaboration	11	34-44	11
Sub-total	44		44
Part II- The effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics			
1. Logarithmic Functions	11	45-55	11
2. Simple Interest	11	56-66	11
3. Compound Interest	11	67-77	11
4. Functions and their Graphs	11	78-88	11
5. Basic Business Mathematics	11	89-99	11
Sub-total	55		56
Total	99	1-90	100

Procedure

The researcher requested first the permission of the Division Superintendent of Division of Quezon, the Public Schools District Supervisor of Division of Quezon, and the school heads of different high schools are included in the study to allow her to distribute questionnaires and conduct interviews for the data needed in the study.

Upon approval, the researcher approached Senior High School teachers and request them to answer the questionnaires that are distributed to them.

Finalization of the Research Instrument. Senior High School teachers as respondents of the study was given four (4) days to answer the questions in the research-made instrument without disrupting their classes.

Retrieval of the Questionnaires. The questionnaires was retrieved one hundred percent from the teacher-respondents of different Senior High Schools. The information needed was answered correspondingly. The researcher was grateful to the teacher-respondents for being cooperative and patient in answering the instrument.

Reliability and Validity of the Instrument. To measure the internal consistency of the instrument, Kuder-Richardson Formula 21 was used. After the retrieval of the questionnaires, reliability was computed using the formula.

Study Procedure. In order that the conduct of the study becomes systematic, the researcher designed a time schedule.

1. Presented the research proposal.
2. Reflected all the suggestions and recommendations during the proposal.
3. Sought permission from higher authorities to conduct the study (through channel).
4. Constructed the questionnaire for the respondents.
5. Validated the instrument.
6. Conducted the dry run.
7. Finalized the instrument for its reliability.
8. Administered and collected the questionnaires from the respondents.
9. Tallied, tabulated, and plotted the data on tables and shown in figures.
10. Presented, interpreted and analyzed the data.
11. Validated the instrument.
12. Conducted the dry run.
13. Finalized the instrument for its reliability.
14. Administered and collected the questionnaires from the respondents.
15. Tallied, tabulated, and plotted the data on tables and shown in figures.
16. Presented, interpreted and analyzed the data.
17. Encoded.
18. Submitted for pre-oral defense.
19. Reflected all the suggestions and recommendations during the pre-oral.
20. Submitted for final defense.
21. Finalized the manuscript.
22. Submitted final copies to CHED.
23. Secured special order.
24. Submitted results to the concerned authorities.
25. Published the research output.

Data Analysis

In the analysis of the data, the researcher used the following statistical tools: Weighted mean, frequency count, percentage, ranking, and Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance W.

The Weighted mean, frequency count, percentage, and ranking was employed to determine the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics and the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics.

The Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance W was used to determine significance of agreement on the rank orders of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics and the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics.

The significance of agreement was determined by the corresponding chi-square formula by Siegel (1988). The level of significance was set at 0.05.

Results and Discussion

The Extent of the Level of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in General Mathematics in terms of: Flexibility, Fluency, Originality and Elaboration

Flexibility. Shown in Table 3 are the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of Flexibility.

Ranked in descending order, were: Group activities promote flexibility as learners discuss and combine their unique perspectives, leading to creative problem-solving approaches, (4.21); Extends when mathematical concepts are applied to real-world situations,

encouraging learners to adapt their knowledge to diverse scenarios, (4.20); The use of technology allows learners to explore mathematical problems dynamically, fostering adaptability and creativity in problem-solving, (4.18); Assessed through methods beyond traditional exams, such as projects or presentations, showcasing a broader range of skills and flexibility, (4.15); The inclusion of open-ended questions challenges learners to think beyond standard procedures and fosters a flexible mindset in problem-solving, (4.15); Analyzing and recognizing patterns in mathematical problems encourages a creative approach, as learners develop strategies based on observed regularities, (4.14); The extent of creative problem-solving in mathematics is evident through the wide array of problem types encountered, ranging from algebraic concepts to propositional logic, (4.10); Showcased as learners can approach a problem in various ways, demonstrating that there's often more than one path to a solution, (4.09); The ability to reframe a problem showcases flexibility, emphasizing that creative solutions can emerge from looking at a problem in different ways, (4.01); and The integration of mathematics with other disciplines emphasizes the adaptability of mathematical problem-solving skills across different fields, (4.00) were all rated Much Evident.

Table 3. *The Extent of the Level of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in General Mathematics in terms of Flexibility*

Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
1. The extent of creative problem-solving in mathematics is evident through the wide array of problem types encountered, ranging from algebraic concepts to propositional logic.	3.75	ME	9	4.00	ME	9.5	4.56	ME	1	4.10	ME	7
2. Showcased as learners can approach a problem in various ways, demonstrating that there's often more than one path to a solution.	3.87	ME	8	4.15	ME	4.5	4.24	ME	8	4.09	ME	8
3. Extends when mathematical concepts are applied to real-world situations, encouraging learners to adapt their knowledge to diverse scenarios.	4.20	ME	1	4.29	ME	2	4.12	ME	9	4.20	ME	2
4. The integration of mathematics with other disciplines emphasizes the adaptability of mathematical problem-solving skills across different fields.	3.93	ME	6	4.12	ME	6	3.96	ME	10	4.00	ME	10
5. The inclusion of open-ended questions challenges learners to think beyond standard procedures and fosters a flexible mindset in problem-solving.	3.92	ME	7	4.09	ME	7	4.44	ME	2	4.15	ME	5
6. The ability to reframe a problem showcases flexibility, emphasizing that creative solutions can emerge from looking at a problem in different ways.	3.72	ME	10	4.00	ME	9.5	4.32	ME	7	4.01	ME	9
7. Analyzing and recognizing patterns in mathematical problems encourages a creative approach, as learners develop strategies based on observed regularities.	3.98	ME	2	4.03	ME	8	4.40	ME	3.5	4.14	ME	6
8. Group activities promote flexibility as learners discuss and combine their unique perspectives, leading to creative problem-solving approaches.	3.95	ME	3.5	4.32	ME	1	4.36	ME	5.5	4.21	ME	1
9. The use of technology allows learners to explore mathematical problems dynamically, fostering adaptability and creativity in problem-solving.	3.94	ME	5	4.21	ME	3	4.40	ME	3.5	4.18	ME	3
10. Assessed through methods beyond traditional exams, such as projects or presentations, showcasing a broader range of skills and flexibility.	3.95	ME	3.5	4.15	ME	4.5	4.36	ME	5.5	4.15	ME	4
Average	3.92	ME		4.14	ME		4.32	ME		4.12	ME	

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Very Much Evident (VME); 3.50–4.49 – Much Evident (ME); 2.50–3.49 – Evident (E); 1.50–2.49 – Fairly Evident (FE); 1.00–1.49 – Not At All (NA)

The average weighted mean of the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of Flexibility was 4.12 or Much Evident. This implies that learners in General Mathematics are highly encouraged to engage in creative problem-solving practices that promote flexibility. Various methods such as group activities, real-world applications, technology usage, alternative assessment approaches, open-ended questions, pattern recognition, and interdisciplinary integration

contribute to fostering adaptability, creativity, and a flexible mindset in problem-solving within the realm of mathematics. It indicates a strong presence of these factors and supports the notion that flexibility is a key aspect of creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics.

Moreover, according to Isyrofinnisak, F & Kusmayadi, Tri Atmojo & Fitriana, Laila. (2020), a key learning outcome in problem-solving domains is the development of flexible knowledge, where learners know multiple strategies and adaptively choose efficient strategies. Two interventions hypothesized to improve flexibility in problem solving were experimentally evaluated: prompts to discover multiple strategies and direct instruction on multiple strategies. Participants were 132 sixth-grade students who solved linear equations for three hours. Both interventions improved students' flexibility in problem solving and did not replace, nor interfere with, one another. Overall, the study provides causal evidence that exposure to multiple strategies leads to improved flexibility in problem solving and that discovery learning and direct instruction are compatible instructional approaches.

Fluency. Reflected in Table 4 are the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of Fluency.

The indicators were arranged in descending order as follows: Learners rapidly apply mathematical concepts to solve problems creatively, showcasing both speed and depth of understanding, (4.10); Reflected in the automatic execution of basic mathematical operations, allowing learners to focus on the creative aspects of problem-solving, (4.08); Augmented when learners fluently identify and correct errors without interrupting the overall problem-solving flow, (4.06); Demonstrated when learners smoothly integrate multiple mathematical concepts in a single problem-solving scenario, showcasing a holistic understanding, (4.05); Involves the adaptive use of strategies, selecting and applying them quickly and accurately based on the nature of the problem, (4.01); Involves the ability to perform calculations mentally, reducing the reliance on written steps and enhancing problem-solving speed, (3.99); Extends to the quick identification and utilization of patterns in mathematical problems, enabling efficient problem-solving through established connections, (3.99); Demonstrated when learners seamlessly transition between different concepts, recognizing connections and applying strategies cohesively, (3.98); Seen in the ability to dynamically adjust problem-solving approaches based on the complexity of the given mathematical task, (3.96); and Learners consistently apply algorithms accurately, freeing cognitive resources for creative problem-solving within the established frameworks, (3.94) were all rated Much Evident.

Table 4. *The Extent of the Level of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in General Mathematics in terms of Fluency*

	Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
		Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
1.	Learners rapidly apply mathematical concepts to solve problems creatively, showcasing both speed and depth of understanding.	3.85	ME	3.5	4.12	ME	1.5	4.32	ME	2	4.10	ME	1
2.	Involves the ability to perform calculations mentally, reducing the reliance on written steps and enhancing problem-solving speed.	3.87	ME	2	3.83	ME	10	4.28	ME	5	3.99	ME	6
3.	Reflected in the automatic execution of basic mathematical operations, allowing learners to focus on the creative aspects of problem-solving.	3.89	ME	1	4.12	ME	1.5	4.24	ME	8	4.08	ME	2
4.	Demonstrated when learners seamlessly transition between different concepts, recognizing connections and applying strategies cohesively.	3.64	ME	10	4.03	ME	4	4.28	ME	5	3.98	ME	8
5.	Involves the adaptive use of strategies, selecting and applying them quickly and accurately based on the nature of the problem.	3.75	ME	7	4.00	ME	6.5	4.28	ME	5	4.01	ME	5
6.	Learners consistently apply algorithms accurately, freeing cognitive resources for creative problem-solving within the established frameworks.	3.74	ME	8	3.85	ME	9	4.24	ME	8	3.94	ME	10
7.	Extends to the quick identification and utilization of patterns in mathematical problems, enabling efficient problem-solving through established connections.	3.72	ME	9	4.00	ME	6.5	4.24	ME	8	3.99	ME	7
8.	Seen in the ability to dynamically adjust problem-solving approaches based on the complexity of the given mathematical task.	3.78	ME	6	4.03	ME	4	4.08	ME	10	3.96	ME	9
9.	Demonstrated when learners smoothly	3.85	ME	3.5	3.97	ME	8	4.32	ME	2	4.05	ME	4

integrate multiple mathematical concepts in a single problem-solving scenario, showcasing a holistic understanding.												
10. Augmented when learners fluently identify and correct errors without interrupting the overall problem-solving flow.	3.82	ME	5	4.03	ME	4	4.32	ME	2	4.06	ME	3
	Average	3.79	ME	4.00	ME		4.26	ME		4.02	ME	

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Very Much Evident (VME); 3.50–4.49 – Much Evident (ME); 2.50–3.49 – Evident (E); 1.50–2.49 – Fairly Evident (FE); 1.00–1.49 – Not At All (NA)

The average weighted mean of the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of Fluency was 4.02 rated Much Evident. This implies that learners in General Mathematics exhibit a high level of fluency in their creative mathematical problem-solving practices. They demonstrate the ability to swiftly apply mathematical concepts, execute basic operations automatically, identify and correct errors seamlessly, and integrate multiple concepts holistically in problem-solving scenarios. The average weighted mean of 4.02, rated Much Evident, suggests that fluency is a prominent aspect of their problem-solving skills.

Additionally, their capacity to adapt strategies quickly, perform mental calculations, identify patterns efficiently, transition between concepts smoothly, adjust problem-solving approaches dynamically based on complexity, and apply algorithms accurately showcases their adeptness in handling mathematical problems with speed and precision. This fluency in problem-solving allows learners to dedicate cognitive resources to the creative aspects of mathematical tasks, contributing to a comprehensive and efficient problem-solving process in General Mathematics.

In relation to this, Bautista, R.G. (2013) on the students’ procedural fluency and written-mathematical explanation on constructed response tasks in physics. It was found out that their procedural fluency on constructed response tasks is significantly related to their written-mathematical explanation ability, and a significant difference on their performance when grouped according to their mathematical and English ability. The students’ procedural fluency is dependent to their mathematical ability, both algebraic and trigonometric, while their written-mathematical explanation is associated to their English ability.

Originality. Gleaned in Table 5 are the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of Originality.

The indicators were ranked in descending order as follows: Learners develop personalized problem-solving methods that reflect their individual thinking and learning styles, (4.22); Learners produce unique mathematical artifacts, such as visual representations, that convey creative insights, (4.16); Learners devise innovative strategies that go beyond conventional methods, showcasing a high level of originality, (4.15); Originality is highlighted when learners apply mathematical concepts in ways that go beyond standard applications, demonstrating a unique and imaginative understanding, (4.12); The learners create new mathematical models or adapt existing ones in original ways to address real-world problems, (4.09); Learners integrate ideas from various disciplines into their mathematical problem-solving, fostering a cross-disciplinary approach, (4.06); Learners display originality when they formulate problems in novel ways, introducing unconventional perspectives that challenge traditional problem-solving approaches, (4.01); Learners creatively synthesize diverse mathematical concepts to develop novel problem-solving frameworks, (3.99); Learners decompose problems in unconventional ways, revealing a capacity to approach challenges from unique angles, (3.90); and Learners leverage technology in inventive ways, utilizing tools and platforms beyond standard applications for creative solutions, (3.86) were interpreted as Much Evident.

Table 5. *The Extent of the Level of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in General Mathematics in terms of Originality*

Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
1. Learners devise innovative strategies that go beyond conventional methods, showcasing a high level of originality.	3.77	ME	6	4.12	ME	4	4.56	ME	1	4.15	ME	3
2. Learners display originality when they formulate problems in novel ways, introducing unconventional perspectives that challenge traditional problem-solving approaches.	3.83	ME	5	3.91	ME	8	4.28	ME	5	4.01	ME	7
3. Originality is highlighted when learners apply mathematical concepts in ways that go beyond standard applications, demonstrating a unique and imaginative understanding.	3.93	ME	3	4.18	ME	2	4.24	ME	7.5	4.12	ME	4
4. Learners decompose problems in unconventional ways, revealing a capacity to approach challenges from unique angles.	3.66	ME	10	3.88	ME	9	4.16	ME	9	3.90	ME	9

5.	Learners develop personalized problem-solving methods that reflect their individual thinking and learning styles.	4.03	ME	1	4.15	ME	3	4.48	ME	2.5	4.22	ME	1
6.	Learners integrate ideas from various disciplines into their mathematical problem-solving, fostering a cross-disciplinary approach.	3.87	ME	4	4.03	ME	6	4.28	ME	5	4.06	ME	6
7.	The learners create new mathematical models or adapt existing ones in original ways to address real-world problems.	3.73	ME	8	4.06	ME	5	4.48	ME	2.5	4.09	ME	5
8.	Learners leverage technology in inventive ways, utilizing tools and platforms beyond standard applications for creative solutions.	3.69	ME	9	3.77	ME	10	4.12	ME	10	3.86	ME	10
9.	Learners creatively synthesize diverse mathematical concepts to develop novel problem-solving frameworks.	3.75	ME	7	3.94	ME	7	4.28	ME	5	3.99	ME	8
10.	Learners produce unique mathematical artifacts, such as visual representations, that convey creative insights.	3.96	ME	2	4.29	ME	1	4.24	ME	7.5	4.16	ME	2
Average		3.82	ME		4.03	ME		4.31	ME		4.06	ME	

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Very Much Evident (VME); 3.50–4.49 – Much Evident (ME); 2.50–3.49 – Evident (E); 1.50–2.49 – Fairly Evident (FE); 1.00–1.49 – Not At All (NA)

The average weighted mean of the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of Originality was 4.06 or Much Evident. This implies that they demonstrate a range of original approaches such as developing personalized problem-solving methods that align with their unique thinking and learning styles, producing unique mathematical artifacts, devising innovative strategies that surpass conventional methods, and applying mathematical concepts in unconventional and imaginative ways.

Furthermore, learners showcase originality by creating new mathematical models or adapting existing ones to tackle real-world issues creatively, integrating ideas from different disciplines into their problem-solving processes, formulating problems in novel ways to challenge traditional approaches, and synthesizing diverse mathematical concepts to construct innovative problem-solving frameworks. Their capacity to decompose problems unconventionally and leverage technology inventively also contributes to their originality in approaching mathematical problem-solving tasks. This emphasis on originality not only enhances their creativity but also fosters a deeper and more innovative understanding of mathematics within the context of General Mathematics.

Bishara, S., & Hui, S. K. F. (2016) research study investigates the ability of students to tackle the solving of unique mathematical problems in the domain of numerical series, verbal and formal, and its influence on the motivation of junior high students with learning disabilities in the Arab sector. The findings fully supported the hypothesis, as well allowing a second hypothesis to arise. It is recommended to use a challenge in the field of mathematical tasks, as the present study found that the use of these contents may contribute to improving the level of motivation for learning, and as a result has implications for a variety of pedagogical realm-contracting effects, such as reducing the phenomenon molt, promoting student achievement, and improving social relations.

Elaboration. Presented in Table 6 are the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of Elaboration.

The indicators were ranked in descending order as follows: Provide detailed narratives that explain the thought processes behind their problem-solving approaches, (4.27); Articulate the strategies employed, offering clear explanations, (4.26); Discuss how mathematical problem-solving connects to real-world scenarios, demonstrating an application-oriented approach, (4.26); Connect problem-solving processes explicitly to prior knowledge, demonstrating a deep understanding, (4.15); Discuss challenges encountered during problem-solving, providing insights into resilience and adaptability, (4.14); Elaborate on the identification of patterns or trends within the problem, (4.12); Consider and elaborate on multiple perspectives, showcasing a holistic approach, (4.11); Reflect on the significance of results, connecting them to broader implications and mathematical concepts, (4.09); Provide thorough justifications for decisions made during the problem-solving process, (4.05); and Explore alternative approaches, discussing choices and implications of different strategies, (4.04) were all interpreted as Much Evident.

The average weighted mean of the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of Elaboration was 4.15 interpreted as Much Evident. This implies that these learners can explicitly link their problem-solving processes to prior knowledge, showing a deep understanding of mathematical concepts. They discuss challenges encountered, offering insights into their resilience and adaptability. By identifying patterns and trends, considering multiple perspectives, and reflecting on the broader implications of their results, they showcase a comprehensive and holistic approach. Providing thorough justifications for their decisions and exploring alternative approaches further highlights their adeptness in handling mathematical problems with a well-rounded and detailed perspective. This level of elaboration enables learners to engage deeply with mathematical tasks, enhancing both their understanding and their ability to apply mathematical concepts effectively.

Table 6. *The Extent of the Level of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in General Mathematics in terms of Elaboration*

Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
1. Provide detailed narratives that explain the thought processes behind their problem-solving approaches.	3.96	ME	4	4.29	ME	2	4.56	ME	1	4.27	ME	1
2. Articulate the strategies employed, offering clear explanations.	4.11	ME	1	4.15	ME	7	4.52	ME	2	4.26	ME	2.5
3. Provide thorough justifications for decisions made during the problem-solving process.	3.91	ME	5.5	4.03	ME	9	4.20	ME	9.5	4.05	ME	9
4. Explore alternative approaches, discussing choices and implications of different strategies.	3.83	ME	7	4.00	ME	10	4.28	ME	6.5	4.04	ME	10
5. Reflect on the significance of results, connecting them to broader implications and mathematical concepts.	3.79	ME	8	4.24	ME	3.5	4.24	ME	8	4.09	ME	8
6. Connect problem-solving processes explicitly to prior knowledge, demonstrating a deep understanding.	4.00	ME	3	4.24	ME	3.5	4.20	ME	9.5	4.15	ME	4
7. Consider and elaborate on multiple perspectives, showcasing a holistic approach.	3.76	ME	10	4.09	ME	8	4.48	ME	3	4.11	ME	7
8. Discuss challenges encountered during problem-solving, providing insights into resilience and adaptability.	3.91	ME	5.5	4.18	ME	5.5	4.32	ME	5	4.14	ME	5
9. Elaborate on the identification of patterns or trends within the problem.	3.77	ME	9	4.18	ME	5.5	4.40	ME	4	4.12	ME	6
10. Discuss how mathematical problem-solving connects to real-world scenarios, demonstrating an application-oriented approach.	4.09	ME	2	4.41	ME	1	4.28	ME	6.5	4.26	ME	2.5
Average	3.91	ME		4.18	ME		4.35	ME		4.15	ME	

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Very Much Evident (VME); 3.50–4.49 – Much Evident (ME); 2.50–3.49 – Evident (E); 1.50–2.49 – Fairly Evident (FE); 1.00–1.49 – Not At All (NA)

Guzman(2018) study is to understand the mathematical problem-solving strategies among student teachers. Findings revealed that the problem-solving strategies among student teachers in the Problem-Solving subject are cognitive, metacognitive and other strategies. The cognitive strategies used by the student teachers are rehearsal, elaboration, and organization. The metacognitive strategies are critical thinking and self-regulation. Other strategies are overlapping the cognitive and metacognitive strategies. These are prediction/orientation, planning, monitoring, and evaluating. The findings also suggest significant influence of the strategies on the academic performance of the student teachers.

The Summary of the Extent of the Level of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in General Mathematics

The summary of the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics in terms of Flexibility, Fluency, Originality and Elaboration is presented in Table 7.

Table 7. *The Summary of the Extent of the Level of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in General Mathematics*

Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
Flexibility	3.92	ME	1	4.14	ME	2	4.32	ME	2	4.12	ME	2
Fluency	3.79	ME	4	4.00	ME	4	4.26	ME	4	4.02	ME	4
Originality	3.82	ME	3	4.03	ME	3	4.31	ME	3	4.06	ME	3
Elaboration	3.91	ME	2	4.18	ME	1	4.35	ME	1	4.15	ME	1
Average	3.86	ME		4.09	ME		4.31	ME		4.09	ME	

As shown, the following areas arranged in descending order, were: Elaboration, (4.15); Flexibility, (4.12); Originality, (4.06); and Fluency, (4.02) were all rated Much Evident.

The average weighted mean of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics among the different types of schools in Calauag West District was 4.09 or Much Evident. This implies that learners in General Mathematics consistently demonstrate high levels of elaboration, flexibility, originality, and fluency in their problem-solving practices. They are adept at providing detailed explanations, adapting strategies, generating unique solutions, and executing mathematical operations swiftly and accurately. This comprehensive skill set highlights their proficiency and effectiveness in tackling mathematical challenges creatively and efficiently.

The paper by Bradshaw (2017) focuses on the development of problem-solving skills in mathematics, The findings suggest that while there is often a focus on attainment, it's essential to create an environment where the emphasis is not solely on finding the right answer but also on exploring the diverse aspects of mathematics and problem-solving.

The Test of Significant Agreement on the Rank Orders of the Extent of the Level of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices of Learners in General Mathematics

To test the significant agreement on the rank order of the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices of learners in General Mathematics along the aforementioned aspects, the Kendall Coefficient of Concordance W and the corresponding Chi-square were computed.

Table 8 reflects the data on the summation of the squared deviation from the mean, computed W, computed Chi-Square, degree of freedom, significance of agreement, and the decision on the null hypothesis.

The summation of squared deviation from the mean for Flexibility, was 261; Fluency, 309.5; Originality, was 482.5; and Elaboration, 320.5.

It could be discerned from the table that the Coefficient of Concordance W and the computed chi-square on level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices of learners in General Mathematics along the aforementioned aspects were: Flexibility, 0.352, and 9.49($p>0.05$); Fluency, 0.417, and 11.25($p>0.05$); Originality, 0.650, and 17.55($p<0.05$); and Elaboration, 0.432, and 11.65($p>0.05$).

Table 8. *The Test of Significant Agreement on the Rank Orders of the Extent of the Level of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices of Learners in General Mathematics*

Indicators	Flexibility	Fluency	Originality	Elaboration
Summation of the Squared Deviation from the Mean	261	309.5	482.5	320.5
Number of Indicators	10	10	10	10
Coefficient of Concordance W	0.352	0.417	0.650	0.432
Computed χ^2	9.49	11.25	17.55	11.65
Degree of Freedom	9	9	9	9
Tabular χ^2 value at 0.05	16.92	16.92	16.92	16.92
0.025	19.02	19.02	19.02	19.02
0.01	21.67	21.67	21.67	21.67
0.001	23.59	23.59	23.59	23.59
0.005	27.88	27.88	27.88	27.88
Decision on H ₀	Accepted	Accepted	Rejected	Accepted
Significance of Agreement	Not Significant	Not Significant	0.05	Not Significant

Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted for Flexibility, Fluency, and Elaboration, indicating no significant agreement on the rank orders of these aspects. However, the null hypothesis was rejected for Originality, showing significant agreement on its rank order. The findings indicate that there is no significant agreement on the rank orders of Flexibility, Fluency, and Elaboration, while there is significant agreement on the rank order of Originality in the creative mathematical problem-solving practices of learners in General Mathematics. This implies that learners exhibit consistent perceptions and evaluations regarding Originality in their problem-solving approaches, while their perceptions of Flexibility, Fluency, and Elaboration are more varied and less consistent. The acceptance of the null hypothesis for Flexibility, Fluency, and Elaboration indicates a lack of strong consensus among these aspects, highlighting the need for more focused and uniform strategies to enhance these areas in mathematical problem-solving education.

Moreover, students regard Mathematics as one of the most challenging topics in school, yet it is an important subject. Mathematics is the study of assumptions, properties, and applications. It must retain the order of assumptions, properties, and applications when teaching. To achieve the desired goal of teaching Mathematics, this order must be preserved in projects (Yadav, 2017).

The Extent of the Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance of the Learners in General Mathematics

The extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along: Logarithmic Functions, Simple Interest, Compound Interest Functions and their Graphs, and Basic Business Mathematics.

Logarithmic Functions. Table 9 shows the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Logarithmic Functions.

The indicators were arranged in descending order as follows: Contributes to a positive and engaging learning experience, motivating learners to explore the subject further, (4.34); Enhances learners' ability to understand and apply the concept to real-world scenarios, (4.33); Improved performance on assessments and exams, (4.30); Logarithmic problem-solving practices contribute to improved critical thinking skills among Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics, (4.24); Connects mathematical concepts to other disciplines,

fostering interdisciplinary understanding, (4.24); Explore various problem-solving strategies, promoting versatility in their approach, (4.23); Enhances learners' appreciation for the role of logarithms in diverse scientific and mathematical contexts, (4.17); Exhibit increased confidence and competence in handling complex mathematical challenges, (4.16); Fosters a deeper understanding of exponential relationships and their inverse nature, (4.12); and Facilitate a more profound grasp of logarithmic properties and their applications, (3.94) were all rated Very Much Effective.

Table 9. *The Extent of the Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance of the Learners in General Mathematics along Logarithmic Functions*

Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
1. Enhances learners' ability to understand and apply the concept to real-world scenarios.	4.06	ME	1	4.44	ME	2.5	4.48	ME	2.5	4.33	ME	2
2. Logarithmic problem-solving practices contribute to improved critical thinking skills among Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics.	3.98	ME	3	4.35	ME	7.5	4.40	ME	6	4.24	ME	4
3. Fosters a deeper understanding of exponential relationships and their inverse nature.	3.88	ME	7	4.03	ME	9	4.44	ME	5	4.12	ME	9
4. Exhibit increased confidence and competence in handling complex mathematical challenges.	3.90	ME	5	4.41	ME	4.5	4.16	ME	9.5	4.16	ME	8
5. Facilitate a more profound grasp of logarithmic properties and their applications.	3.70	ME	10	3.97	ME	10	4.16	ME	9.5	3.94	ME	10
6. Improved performance on assessments and exams.	4.04	ME	2	4.38	ME	6	4.48	ME	2.5	4.30	ME	3
7. Contributes to a positive and engaging learning experience, motivating learners to explore the subject further.	3.97	ME	4	4.56	ME	1	4.48	ME	2.5	4.34	ME	1
8. Enhances learners' appreciation for the role of logarithms in diverse scientific and mathematical contexts.	3.84	ME	8	4.35	ME	7.5	4.32	ME	8	4.17	ME	7
9. Connects mathematical concepts to other disciplines, fostering interdisciplinary understanding.	3.83	ME	9	4.41	ME	4.5	4.48	ME	2.5	4.24	ME	5
10. Explore various problem-solving strategies, promoting versatility in their approach.	3.89	ME	6	4.44	ME	2.5	4.36	ME	7	4.23	ME	6
Average	3.91	ME		4.33	ME		4.38	ME		4.21	ME	

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Very Much Evident (VME); 3.50–4.49 – Much Evident (ME); 2.50–3.49 – Evident (E); 1.50–2.49 – Fairly Evident (FE); 1.00–1.49 – Not At All (NA)

The average weighted mean of the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Logarithmic Functions was 4.21. This implies that the creative mathematical problem-solving practices are highly effective in improving the performance of learners in General Mathematics, particularly in the context of Logarithmic Functions. The high ratings across various indicators suggest that these practices significantly enhance the learning experience by making it more engaging and motivating. They help learners better understand and apply logarithmic concepts to real-world scenarios, improve performance on assessments, and develop critical thinking skills.

Moreover, these practices foster interdisciplinary understanding by connecting mathematical concepts to other disciplines and promoting versatility in problem-solving strategies. They also enhance learners' appreciation of the role of logarithms in various contexts, boost confidence and competence in handling complex mathematical challenges, and deepen understanding of exponential relationships and logarithmic properties. With an average weighted mean of 4.21, the overall effectiveness of these creative problem-solving practices is rated as Very Much Effective, highlighting their substantial impact on learners' performance in General Mathematics.

Makgakga et al., (2013) discusses the benefits of using a transformation approach in the teaching and learning of exponential and logarithmic functions in a grade 12 mathematics classrooms. The findings indicated that the interventional strategy had an impact on academic performances of the learners. Furthermore, learners had begun to understand and apply the learnt strategy when solving problems related to both exponential and logarithmic functions.

Simple Interest. Table 10 depicts the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Simple Interest.

The indicators were ranked in descending order as follows: Creative problem-solving in simple interest enhances learners' ability to understand and apply the concept to real-world scenarios, (4.40); Simple interest problem-solving practices contribute to improved

critical thinking skills among Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics, (4.31); Learners engaging in creative simple interest problem-solving exhibit increased confidence and competence in handling complex mathematical challenges, (4.24); The application of creative problem-solving in simple interest fosters a deeper understanding of financial literacy and critical thinking skills, (4.20); The effectiveness of creative problem-solving in simple interest is reflected in learners' improved performance on assessments and exams, (4.20); Creative approaches to simple interest problem-solving facilitate a more profound grasp of financial concepts and their practical applications, (4.18); The application of creativity in simple interest problem-solving connects mathematical concepts to other disciplines, fostering interdisciplinary understanding, (4.18); Creative problem-solving in simple interest contributes to a positive and engaging learning experience, motivating learners to explore the subject further, (4.15); Simple interest problem-solving practices encourage learners to explore various problem-solving strategies, promoting versatility in their approach, (4.14); and Integrating creativity in simple interest problem-solving enhances learners' appreciation for the role of simple interest in financial decision-making in personal and professional contexts, (4.11) were rated Much Effective.

Table 10. *The Extent of the Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance of the Learners in General Mathematics along Simple Interest*

Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
1. Creative problem-solving in simple interest enhances learners' ability to understand and apply the concept to real-world scenarios.	4.13	ME	1	4.47	ME	1	4.60	ME	1.5	4.40	ME	1
2. Simple interest problem-solving practices contribute to improved critical thinking skills among Grade 11 learners in General Mathematics.	4.05	ME	2	4.41	ME	2	4.48	ME	3	4.31	ME	2
3. The application of creative problem-solving in simple interest fosters a deeper understanding of financial literacy and critical thinking skills.	3.97	ME	5	4.18	ME	8.5	4.44	ME	5	4.20	ME	5
4. Learners engaging in creative simple interest problem-solving exhibit increased confidence and competence in handling complex mathematical challenges.	4.00	ME	3.5	4.29	ME	3.5	4.44	ME	5	4.24	ME	3
5. Creative approaches to simple interest problem-solving facilitate a more profound grasp of financial concepts and their practical applications.	3.93	ME	7	4.18	ME	8.5	4.44	ME	5	4.18	ME	6.5
6. The effectiveness of creative problem-solving in simple interest is reflected in learners' improved performance on assessments and exams.	4.00	ME	3.5	4.24	ME	5.5	4.36	ME	9	4.20	ME	4
7. Simple interest problem-solving practices encourage learners to explore various problem-solving strategies, promoting versatility in their approach	3.91	ME	8	4.12	ME	10	4.40	ME	7.5	4.14	ME	9
8. The application of creativity in simple interest problem-solving connects mathematical concepts to other disciplines, fostering interdisciplinary understanding.	3.94	ME	6	4.21	ME	7	4.40	ME	7.5	4.18	ME	6.5
9. Integrating creativity in simple interest problem-solving enhances learners' appreciation for the role of simple interest in financial decision-making in personal and professional contexts.	3.81	ME	9	4.24	ME	5.5	4.28	ME	10	4.11	ME	10
10. Creative problem-solving in simple interest contributes to a positive and engaging learning experience, motivating learners to explore the subject further.	3.57	ME	10	4.29	ME	3.5	4.60	ME	1.5	4.15	ME	8
	Average	3.93	ME	4.26	ME		4.44	ME		4.21	ME	

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Very Much Evident (VME); 3.50–4.49 – Much Evident (ME); 2.50–3.49 – Evident (E); 1.50–2.49 – Fairly Evident (FE); 1.00–1.49 – Not At All (NA)

The average weighted mean of the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Simple Interest was 4.21 or Much Effective. This implies that the creative mathematical problem-solving practices are highly effective in improving learners' performance in General Mathematics, specifically in the area of Simple Interest. The indicators suggest that these practices significantly enhance learners' understanding and application of simple interest concepts to real-world scenarios, boost critical thinking skills, and increase confidence and competence in handling

complex mathematical challenges.

These practices also foster a deeper understanding of financial literacy, facilitate improved performance on assessments, and promote a more profound grasp of financial concepts and their practical applications. Additionally, they connect mathematical concepts to other disciplines, fostering interdisciplinary understanding, and contribute to a positive and engaging learning experience, motivating learners to explore the subject further. The encouragement of various problem-solving strategies promotes versatility in learners' approaches, and integrating creativity in problem-solving enhances their appreciation for the role of simple interest in financial decision-making.

Cavalcante et. al., (2024) proposes an in-depth mathematics analysis of simple and compound interest through an exploration of the mathematical structures underlying these concepts. Such results indicate opportunities for professional development in regard to secondary mathematics teachers' knowledge of mathematics in the context of simple and compound interest situations.

Compound Interest. Table 11 present the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Compound Interest.

The indicators were arranged in descending order as follows: Deepens learners' comprehension of exponential growth and its financial implications, (4.29); Contributes to a positive and insightful learning experience, preparing learners for complex financial situations, (4.27); Enhanced performance on assessments and financial simulations, (4.26); Encourages learners to explore diverse investment strategies and financial planning, (4.26); Connects mathematical concepts to practical investment scenarios and financial management, (4.21); Improve learners' proficiency in calculating compound interest for varying compounding frequencies, (4.20); Reinforces learners' understanding of compounding over time, (4.19); Foster a deeper understanding of the interplay between interest rates, compounding periods, and investment outcomes, (4.18); Exhibit increased confidence in making informed financial decisions, (4.18); and Enhances learners' ability to analyze and compare different investment scenarios, (4.15) were all interpreted as Much Effective.

Table 11. The Extent of the Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance of the Learners in General Mathematics along Compound Interest

Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
1. Deepens learners' comprehension of exponential growth and its financial implications.	4.00	ME	1.5	4.38	ME	1	4.48	ME	3	4.29	ME	1
2. Enhances learners' ability to analyze and compare different investment scenarios.	4.00	ME	1.5	4.29	ME	6	4.16	ME	10	4.15	ME	10
3. Reinforces learners' understanding of compounding over time.	3.88	ME	10	4.24	ME	9	4.44	ME	5	4.19	ME	7
4. Improve learners' proficiency in calculating compound interest for varying compounding frequencies.	3.89	ME	9	4.35	ME	2.5	4.36	ME	9	4.20	ME	6
5. Enhanced performance on assessments and financial simulations.	3.91	ME	6	4.32	ME	4.5	4.56	ME	1.5	4.26	ME	3
6. Encourages learners to explore diverse investment strategies and financial planning.	3.99	ME	3	4.35	ME	2.5	4.44	ME	5	4.26	ME	4
7. Foster a deeper understanding of the interplay between interest rates, compounding periods, and investment outcomes.	3.90	ME	7.5	4.24	ME	9	4.40	ME	7.5	4.18	ME	8.5
8. Exhibit increased confidence in making informed financial decisions.	3.90	ME	7.5	4.24	ME	9	4.40	ME	7.5	4.18	ME	8.5
9. Connects mathematical concepts to practical investment scenarios and financial management.	3.93	ME	4.5	4.27	ME	7	4.44	ME	5	4.21	ME	5
10. Contributes to a positive and insightful learning experience, preparing learners for complex financial situations.	3.93	ME	4.5	4.32	ME	4.5	4.56	ME	1.5	4.27	ME	2
Average	3.93	ME		4.30	ME		4.42	ME		4.22	ME	

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Very Much Evident (VME); 3.50–4.49 – Much Evident (ME); 2.50–3.49 – Evident (E); 1.50–2.49 – Fairly Evident (FE); 1.00–1.49 – Not At All (NA)

The average weighted mean of the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Compound Interest was 4.22 rated Much Evident. This implies that these practices significantly enhance learners' comprehension of exponential growth and its financial implications, providing a positive and insightful learning experience that prepares them for complex financial situations. These also lead to improved performance on assessments and financial simulations, encourage exploration of diverse investment strategies and financial planning, and connect mathematical concepts to practical investment scenarios and financial management. They improve learners' proficiency in calculating

compound interest for varying compounding frequencies, reinforce their understanding of compounding over time, and foster a deeper understanding of the interplay between interest rates, compounding periods, and investment outcomes.

Pournara(2013)cited that there is increasing acknowledgement that teachers’ knowledge for teaching mathematics is multifaceted and topic specific. Given the paucity of research on the teaching and learning of financial mathematics in general, little can be known about teachers’ knowledge for teaching compound interest. Based on findings from the study, two key student errors are identified: the over-generalisation of linear thinking in multiplicative scenarios, and the over-generalisation of reversible operations in percentage-change scenarios. Taken together, teachers’ knowledge of relevant mathematics, of the banking context and of learners’ conceptions will contribute to building a knowledge-base for teachers’ knowledge for teaching compound interest.

Functions and their Graphs. Table 12 portrays the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Functions and their Graphs.

The indicators were arranged in descending order as follows: Develops learners' analytical skills and understanding of mathematical modeling, (4.41); Encourages learners to explore different types of functions and their applications, (4.34); Reinforces learners' understanding of domain, range, and function behavior, (4.29); Improve learners' proficiency in graphing and interpreting mathematical functions, (4.28); Contributes to a positive and exploratory learning experience, preparing learners for advanced mathematical concepts, (4.28); Enhances learners' ability to interpret and analyze different types of functions, (4.25); Improved performance on function-related assessments and graph analysis, (4.24); Exhibit increased confidence in analyzing and interpreting mathematical models, (4.18); Foster a deeper understanding of the relationships between variables and mathematical representations, (4.15); and Connects mathematical concepts to various real-world applications and scientific phenomena, (4.13) were rated Much Effective.

Table 12. *The Extent of the Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance of the Learners in General Mathematics along Functions and their Graphs*

Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
1. Develops learners' analytical skills and understanding of mathematical modeling.	4.21	ME	1	4.38	ME	3	4.64	ME	1	4.41	ME	1
2. Enhances learners' ability to interpret and analyze different types of functions.	4.14	ME	3	4.21	ME	9	4.40	ME	7.5	4.25	ME	6
3. Reinforces learners' understanding of domain, range, and function behavior.	4.16	ME	2	4.32	ME	5	4.40	ME	7.5	4.29	ME	3
4. Improve learners' proficiency in graphing and interpreting mathematical functions.	4.12	ME	4	4.29	ME	6.5	4.44	ME	5	4.28	ME	4
5. Improved performance on function-related assessments and graph analysis.	3.99	ME	6	4.29	ME	6.5	4.44	ME	5	4.24	ME	7
6. Encourages learners to explore different types of functions and their applications.	4.02	ME	5	4.47	ME	1	4.52	ME	2	4.34	ME	2
7. Foster a deeper understanding of the relationships between variables and mathematical representations.	3.92	ME	10	4.09	ME	10	4.44	ME	5	4.15	ME	9
8. Exhibit increased confidence in analyzing and interpreting mathematical models.	3.98	ME	7	4.24	ME	8	4.32	ME	9	4.18	ME	8
9. Connects mathematical concepts to various real-world applications and scientific phenomena.	3.93	ME	9	4.35	ME	4	4.12	ME	10	4.13	ME	10
10. Contributes to a positive and exploratory learning experience, preparing learners for advanced mathematical concepts	3.95	ME	8	4.41	ME	2	4.48	ME	3	4.28	ME	5
Average	4.04	ME		4.31	ME		4.42	ME		4.26	ME	

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Very Much Evident (VME); 3.50–4.49 – Much Evident (ME); 2.50–3.49 – Evident (E); 1.50–2.49 – Fairly Evident (FE); 1.00–1.49 – Not At All (NA)

The average weighted mean of the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Functions and their Graphs was 4.26 interpreted as Much Effective. This implies that creative mathematical problem-solving practices are highly effective in enhancing the performance of learners in General Mathematics, particularly in the area of Functions and their Graphs. The high ratings indicate that these practices significantly develop learners' analytical skills and understanding of mathematical modeling, encourage exploration of different types of functions and their applications, and strengthen their grasp of key concepts such as domain, range, and function behavior. They also enhance learners' ability to interpret and analyze various types of functions, improve performance on function-related assessments and graph analysis, and increase confidence in analyzing and interpreting mathematical models.

Moreover, they foster a deeper understanding of the relationships between variables and mathematical representations and connect mathematical concepts to real-world applications and scientific phenomena. With an average weighted mean of 4.26, the overall effectiveness of these creative problem-solving practices is rated as Much Effective, underscoring their significant impact on learners'

performance in General Mathematics in the context of Functions and their Graphs.

David (2019) dissertation delves into how undergraduate students interpret expressions in the graphical register within the context of Calculus. It identifies that while graphs are commonly used to illustrate mathematical concepts, students may have unconventional interpretations that can affect their understanding of related content. Past research has focused on students' interpretations of points on graphs but has left a gap in understanding how they interpret and reason with variables and expressions on graphed functions.

The findings highlight that different contexts can evoke different graphical interpretations from the same student, impacting their evaluations of mathematical statements. The dissertation discusses the characteristics of these interpretations, their relation to students' evaluations, the mathematical content involved, and their interpretation of points on graphs. It also considers the implications of these findings for teaching and suggests directions for future research in this area.

Basic Business Mathematics. Table 13 reflects the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Basic Business Mathematics.

The indicators were ranked in descending order as follows: Enhances learners' ability to apply mathematical concepts to practical business scenarios, (4.41); Develops learners' skills in budgeting, financial planning, and resource allocation, (4.40); Contributes to a positive and practical learning experience, preparing learners for challenges in the business world, (4.36); Foster a deeper understanding of the relationship between mathematical models and business applications, (4.28); Connects mathematical concepts to practical business decision-making and strategic planning, (4.27); The effectiveness of creative problem-solving in business mathematics is reflected in learners' improved performance on business-related assessments and simulations, (4.24); Reinforces learners' understanding of profit, loss, and financial decision-making, (4.20); Improve learners' proficiency in calculating and analyzing financial ratios and performance metrics, (4.20); Encourages learners to explore diverse business scenarios and make strategic decisions, (4.19); and Exhibit increased confidence in applying mathematical concepts to real-world business challenges, (4.18) were all rated Much Effective.

Table 13. *The Extent of the Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance of the Learners in General Mathematics along Basic Business Mathematics*

Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
1. Enhances learners' ability to apply mathematical concepts to practical business scenarios.	4.24	ME	1	4.50	ME	1	4.48	ME	6.5	4.41	ME	1
2. Reinforces learners' understanding of profit, loss, and financial decision-making.	4.13	ME	2	4.00	ME	10	4.48	ME	6.5	4.20	ME	7
3. Develops learners' skills in budgeting, financial planning, and resource allocation.	4.12	ME	3	4.41	ME	3	4.68	ME	1	4.40	ME	2
4. Improve learners' proficiency in calculating and analyzing financial ratios and performance metrics.	4.06	ME	7	4.18	ME	6.5	4.36	ME	10	4.20	ME	8
5. The effectiveness of creative problem-solving in business mathematics is reflected in learners' improved performance on business-related assessments and simulations.	4.00	ME	8	4.32	ME	4	4.40	ME	8.5	4.24	ME	6
6. Encourages learners to explore diverse business scenarios and make strategic decisions.	4.07	ME	5.5	4.09	ME	9	4.40	ME	8.5	4.19	ME	9
7. Foster a deeper understanding of the relationship between mathematical models and business applications.	4.10	ME	4	4.18	ME	6.5	4.56	ME	3.5	4.28	ME	4
8. Exhibit increased confidence in applying mathematical concepts to real-world business challenges.	3.88	ME	10	4.15	ME	8	4.52	ME	5	4.18	ME	10
9. Connects mathematical concepts to practical business decision-making and strategic planning.	3.98	ME	9	4.24	ME	5	4.60	ME	2	4.27	ME	5
10. Contributes to a positive and practical learning experience, preparing learners for challenges in the business world.	4.07	ME	5.5	4.44	ME	2	4.56	ME	3.5	4.36	ME	3
Average	4.07	ME		4.25	ME		4.50	ME		4.27	ME	

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Very Much Evident (VME); 3.50–4.49 – Much Evident (ME); 2.50–3.49 – Evident (E); 1.50–2.49 – Fairly Evident (FE); 1.00–1.49 – Not At All (NA)

The average weighted mean of the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Basic Business Mathematics was 4.27 or Much Effective. This implies that

the creative mathematical problem-solving practices significantly improve the performance of learners in both General Mathematics and Basic Business Mathematics. Specifically, the practices are highly effective in enhancing learners' ability to apply mathematical concepts to practical business scenarios, developing skills in budgeting, financial planning, and resource allocation, and contributing to a positive and practical learning experience.

The average weighted mean of 4.27 indicates that across all indicators, the effectiveness is rated as "Much Effective," showcasing a strong positive impact on learners' understanding and application of mathematical concepts in real-world business contexts. This implies that integrating creative problem-solving methods in teaching mathematics leads to better performance, deeper understanding, and increased confidence among learners when dealing with business-related challenges and decision-making.

Özlen, Şerife & Özlen, Muhammed. (2021) on Basic Business Mathematics highlighted that everybody knows the importance of Mathematics in every aspect of the life. While all academic disciplines and their workers need some amount of mathematics, there is no need to overload all of them with complex structures and formulas. Finding the right balance is a hard work. Few books can provide the necessary information without overloading the students. We designed this book to present the right amount of elementary mathematics for junior business faculty students and vocational school students. The book starts with some fundamental concepts and continues with equations, inequalities, absolute value, functions and their use in business life. We prefer to explain the subjects in a very simple way. After the explanation, necessary examples with solutions are provided. At the end of some sections, we provide also "Follow-up Examples" (most of them with solutions) to reinforce the students' knowledge.

The Summary of the Extent of the Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance of the Learners in General Mathematics

Table 14 depicts the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along Logarithm, Simple Interest, Compound Interest, Functions and their Graphs, and Basic Business Mathematics.

As depicted, among five strands, Basic Business Mathematics ranked first with 4.27 mean and interpreted as Much Effective. This was followed by: Functions and their Graphs, (4.26); Compound Interest, (4.22); Logarithm Functions, (4.21); and Simple Interest, (4.21) were also interpreted as Much Effective.

The average weighted mean of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics among the different types of Schools in Calauag West District was 4.23 rated Much Effective. This implies that integrating creative problem-solving approaches into teaching these mathematical concepts yields substantial benefits, leading to improved understanding, application, and performance among learners in General Mathematics across various strands and school settings.

Table 14. *The Summary of the Extent of the Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance of the Learners in General Mathematics*

Indicators	Big Schools			Medium Schools			Small Schools			Average		
	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank	Wx	Int.	Rank
Logarithm	3.91	ME	5	4.33	ME	1	4.38	ME	5	4.21	ME	4.5
Simple Interest	3.93	ME	3.5	4.26	ME	4	4.44	ME	2	4.21	ME	4.5
Compound Interest	3.93	ME	3.5	4.30	ME	3	4.42	ME	3.5	4.22	ME	3
Functions and their Graphs	4.04	ME	2	4.31	ME	2	4.42	ME	3.5	4.26	ME	2
Business Mathematics	4.07	ME	1	4.25	ME	5	4.50	VME	1	4.27	ME	1
Average	3.98	ME		4.29	ME		4.43	ME		4.23	ME	

Legend: 4.50–5.00 – Very Much Evident (VME); 3.50–4.49 – Much Evident (ME); 2.50–3.49 – Evident (E); 1.50–2.49 – Fairly Evident (FE); 1.00–1.49 – Not At All (NA)

Kumar's (2018) study focused on enhancing students' mathematical problem-solving skills through the use of the Bar Model visualization technique. This technique was chosen as a strategy to help students overcome difficulties in solving word problems, a common challenge revealed in previous studies. The results indicated a significant improvement in participants' mathematical problem-solving achievement after implementing the Bar Model technique. The semi-structured interviews further revealed that students' level of understanding and motivation played crucial roles in their performance. Overall, the study suggests that the Bar Model visualization technique can be effective in enhancing students' problem-solving skills and provides guidance for teachers looking to improve their students' mathematical abilities in this area.

The Test of Significant Agreement on the Rank Orders Of The Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance of the Learners in General Mathematics

To test the significant agreement on the rank order of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along the different groups of respondents, the Kendall Coefficient of Concordance W and the corresponding Chi-square were computed.

Table 15 reflects the data on the summation of the squared deviation from the mean, computed W, computed Chi-Square, degree of freedom, significance of agreement, and the decision on the null hypothesis.

The summation of squared deviation from the mean for Logarithm, was 473; Simple Interest, 465; Compound Interest, was 399; Functions and their Graphs, was 402.5; and Basic Business Mathematics, 344.5.

It could be discerned from the table that the Coefficient of Concordance W and the computed chi-square on effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along the different groups of respondents were: Logarithmic Functions 0.637, and 17.20($p < 0.05$); Simple Interest 0.626, and 16.91($p > 0.05$); Compound Interest 0.537, and 14.51($p > 0.05$); Functions and their Graphs 0.542, and 14.64($p > 0.05$); and lastly, Basic Business Mathematics 0.464, and 12.53($p > 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted except for Logarithmic Functions.

Table 15. *Test of Significant Agreement on the Rank Orders of the Effectiveness of the Creative Mathematical Problem-Solving Practices in Improving the Performance of the Learners in General Mathematics*

Indicators	Logarithmic Functions	Simple Interest	Compound Interest	Functions and their Graphs	Basic Business Mathematics
Summation of the Squared Deviation from the Mean	473	465	399	402.5	344.5
Number of Indicators	10	10	10	10	10
Coefficient of Concordance W	0.637	0.626	0.537	0.542	0.464
Computed χ^2	17.20	16.91	14.51	14.64	12.53
Degree of Freedom	9	9	9	9	9
Tabular χ^2 value at 0.05	16.92	16.92	16.92	16.92	16.92
0.025	19.02	19.68	19.68	19.68	19.68
0.01	21.67	21.67	21.67	21.67	21.67
0.005	23.59	23.59	23.59	23.59	23.59
0.001	27.88				
Decision on H ₀	Rejected	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted	Accepted
Significance of Agreement	0.05	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant

The data show that the computed chi-square, only one indicator exceeds the tabular chi-square value at the level of significance of 0.05. This implies that there is no significant agreement among the different groups of respondents regarding the effectiveness of creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of learners in General Mathematics, except for the area of Logarithmic Functions. For Logarithmic Functions, there is a notable agreement in opinion or perception among the respondents compared to the other areas like Simple Interest, Compound Interest, Functions and their Graphs, and Basic Business Mathematics. This means that while there was a general consensus on the effectiveness of these practices across most topics, there might be varying degrees of agreement or disagreement specifically concerning Logarithmic Functions. This information could be valuable for teachers or curriculum makers to understand where there might be agreement in perception or effectiveness of teaching methods, allowing for targeted improvements or adjustments in those specific areas.

Al Kharusi, Ahmed & Al-Abed, Adnan. (2021) study examined the impact of a program based on problem-solving in mathematical problem-solving among 10th grade students. The findings indicated that there were significant statistical differences in mathematical problem-solving test between the experimental and control group due to teaching method in favor of experimental group. The findings indicated that there were no significant statistical differences in mathematical problem-solving test between male and female students. The findings also indicated that there were statistical significance differences in mathematical problem-solving test due to the interaction between and teaching method and gender. The study recommended organizing training workshops for mathematics teachers to introduce programs based on problem solving, training them to build educational programs based on problem solving, and urging them to adopt it due to the positive impact it has shown in teaching mathematics.

Conclusions

Based from the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in General Mathematics are rated Much Evident.

There is no significant agreement on the rank orders of the extent of the level of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices of learners in General Mathematics along the aforementioned aspects except for Originality.

The extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics are Much Effective.

There is no significant agreement on the rank orders of the extent of the effectiveness of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance of the learners in General Mathematics along the different groups of respondents except for Logarithmic Functions

There are policy recommendations generated based on the findings of the study.

Continue and further enhance practices in General Mathematics education. This could involve incorporating more open-ended

problems, encouraging divergent thinking, and fostering a creative mindset among learners.

Encourage learners to come up with unique solutions and approaches that can further develop their creative thinking skills.

Teachers should continue using the practices and explore additional strategies.

Pursuant to the conclusions stated that promote critical thinking, analytical reasoning, and innovative problem-solving techniques.

Tailor teaching methods and interventions based on the specific needs such as targeted exercises, additional support materials, or differentiated instruction.

The Policy recommendations must be adopted.

The following were the suggestions for future research:

Conduct a longitudinal study to track the long-term impact of the creative mathematical problem-solving practices in improving the performance.

Explore the impact of specific professional development programs or training modules for teachers focused on creative mathematical problem-solving practices.

Extend the research scope to explore the transferability of teaching approaches across different subject areas.

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